

DETERMINATION OF A PV MODULE POWER MATRIX WITH AN LED SOLAR SIMULATOR

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ABSTRACT: Energy Rating is a technique that enables a more realistic comparison of PV module performance. In this work, we utilize an LED solar simulator to measure two crucial input parameters for Energy Rating: the power matrix and the spectral responsivity of a poly-Si PV module. The power matrix is measured in a higher resolution compared to the minimum requirements given by the Energy Rating standard IEC 61853 and the obtained dataset is used to determine inter- and extrapolation issues that may arise from the low resolution demanded by the standard. It is shown that for the examined poly-Si module the low resolution is sufficient and yield differences of less than 0.15 % occur. **Keywords:** Energy Rating, Characterisation, Electrical Properties, Qualification and Testing

1 INTRODUCTION

Which PV module performs best under a certain climatic condition? The datasheet of a PV module gives insufficient information to answer this question, as they typically provide a rating under standard test conditions (STC). An STC rating is done at a laboratory-convenient but unrealistic module temperature of 25 °C, an irradiance of 1000 W/m² and with a standardized spectral distribution according to IEC 60904-3 [1]. However, the actual yield of PV modules installed in the field is a consequence of many input parameters like varying module temperatures, resulting from different wind speeds and varying total irradiances, changing spectral distributions and incidence angles between light source and PV module. The IEC 61853 standard [2] provides the necessary toolset to perform such a measurement. However, Energy Rating needs a considerably larger amount of module characteristics that needs to be determined. In this work we present the capabilities of an LED solar simulator that is able to capture two of the four needed input parameters in a single, automated measuring process. This enables us to perform measurements of a matrix of irradiance- and temperature-dependent power values (power matrix) in higher resolutions compared to the minimal requirements given by the standard with little additional effort. We then evaluate if a higher resolution of the power matrix provides less inter- and extrapolation uncertainties and thus justifies the additional measurement effort.

Figure 1: LED solar simulator for PV modules at PTB. The composite picture shows three of the 18 different LED colors built into the system.

2 METHODS

The Energy Rating standard IEC 61853-3 provides the formulas necessary to perform a yield calculation based on six hourly datasets of climatic conditions, given in IEC 61853-4. Beside these datasets given by the standard, the following electrical and optical properties of a PV module are needed to conduct an Energy Rating:

- A matrix of power values at various irradiances (G) and temperatures (T)
- The spectral responsivity (SR) of the module
- Its dependency of wind speed
- The angular responsivity of the module

The determination of the power matrix is described in IEC 61853-1 and the other three input values in IEC 61853-2. In this work, we focus on the measurement of the G-T-power matrix and the SR of the PV module. Compared to STC, the measurements for Energy Rating require more time and effort, especially for laboratories that rely on manually switching neutral density filters in order to achieve different irradiance levels.

Table 1: Power matrix of a p-Si 270 W PV module, rounded to integer values. GT resolution specified by the standard is marked blue, additional measurements are marked orange. The STC is marked with red text color.

irradiance (G)	temperature (T)								
	15 °C	20 °C	25 °C	30 °C	40 °C	50 °C	60 °C	70 °C	75 °C
50 W/m ²	12	12	12	11	11	10	10	9	9
100 W/m ²	26	25	25	24	23	22	21	20	19
200 W/m ²	53	52	51	50	48	46	43	41	40
400 W/m ²	110	107	105	103	99	94	90	86	83
600 W/m ²	166	163	159	156	150	143	137	131	127
800 W/m ²	222	217	213	209	200	192	183	174	170
1000 W/m ²	277	271	266	261	250	239	228	218	212
1100 W/m ²	304	298	293	287	275	263	251	239	234

At PTB, the power matrix is measured with a setup consisting of an LED solar simulator [3, 4] as light source and a temperature chamber to adjust the module temperature. One advantage of the LED-based simulator is its ability to change the irradiance by tuning the LED output for each of its 18 different color channels individually rather than using neutral density or absorbing filters. This greatly reduces the amount of work necessary to conduct a power matrix measurement, since the whole measurement is automated and can be conducted at any desired resolution of irradiance and temperature. In

addition, the SR of the PV module is measured with the same light source, by subsequently modulating each LED channel and intercomparing the resulting short circuit fluctuations to a reference cell. The method is described in detail in [3].

3 MEASUREMENTS

The power values are derived from IV curves measured with a system-integrated curve tracer. The irradiance emitted by the simulator is determined with a traceable WPVS reference cell, calibrated at PTB and temperature stabilized at 25 °C. The module temperature is measured at nine locations on the backside of the device under test and the mean value is taken as module temperature. A spectral mismatch correction is conducted based on the SR curve derived by the LED modulation method described in [3] (**Figure 2**). In order to exactly match the G and T values shown in **Table 1**, corrections were performed according to method 1 of IEC 60891. The corrected IV curves are displayed in **Figure 3**.

The P_{\max} values derived from the IV curves are displayed in **Table 1**. The measurement of the complete power matrix takes about a day, which is mainly due to the long settling time of the module temperature non-uniformity in our temperature chamber.

Figure 2: Spectral responsivity of the tested PV module derived at 18 different wavelengths by LED color modulation.

Figure 3: IV curves of a p-Si PV module measured with an LED solar simulator at all irradiances and temperatures necessary to derive the power matrix used in IEC 61853.

Figure 4: Hourly data (black dots) of module power output for all six climate conditions. Blue dots mark the high-resolution power matrix, red dots the lower resolution of the standard.

Table 2: Yearly yields of the examined p-Si module for the six climate conditions of IEC 61853-4. Shown are the yields with high resolution (HR) and low resolution (LR) of the power matrix.

climate	yield		
	HR / kWh	LR / kWh	Diff / %
temperate coastal	254.53	254.92	-0.154
subtropical arid	552.34	552.31	0.006
subtropical coastal	381.61	381.79	-0.046
high elevation	562.12	562.11	0.002
temperate continental	328.71	328.92	-0.063
tropical humid	403.66	403.47	0.048

4 DATA EVALUATION

As described above, four input values are needed for the Energy Rating calculation according to IEC 61853-3. The angular incidence factor a_r and wind coefficients u_0 and u_1 were not derived in this work, thus values from literature are used [5, 6], since their influence on interpolation errors is minimal compared to the power matrix:

$$u_0 = 25 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}, u_1 = 6.84 \text{ W m}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$$

$$a_r = 0.153$$

The measured power matrix and SR curve are used as input for the Energy Rating calculation of hourly module power for each of the six different climate conditions. An overlay plot of this data together with the input power matrix is shown in **Figure 4**. One can see that the blue-colored squares represent the power matrix and cover the temperature range from 15°C to 75°C and the irradiance range from 50 to 1100 W/m² in a high resolution. The red-colored dots mark the power matrix resolution given by the standard. In the low-resolution power matrix, wide temperature ranges from 25°C to 50°C and from 50°C to 75°C are not covered with data points. All black power values are summarized in order to get the annual yield under a given climate. The whole Energy Rating calculation has been performed for high- and low-resolution power matrix and the yields are shown in **Table 2**. The low resolution shows very little yield differences of -0.15 % or even less, depending on the climate. These differences are also being tracked down locally to the G-T region where these differences originate from by dividing each HR data point of **Figure 4** by its corresponding LR datapoint. While slight improvements for interpolation in the temperature regions around 40°C and 60°C are observed, the mayor differences arise from the region

below 100 W/m², where differences of -5 % or more are apparent at the calculation based on the high resolution power matrix.

5 DISCUSSION

The p-Si power matrix shows a pretty linear behavior along the temperature axis. Thus, a higher temperature resolution is nearly irrelevant for the accuracy of the calculation. Also, extrapolation errors of around 0.25 % at $G = 300 \text{ W/m}^2$, $T = 30^\circ\text{C}$ due to left-out data points in the low-resolution matrix has little to none impact on yield: Not many data points are affected and those who are have a irradiance value of less than 400 W/m². Most of the observed differences in yield calculation originate from the additional data points at 50 W/m². Here, the efficiency of the p-Si PV module decreases slightly non-linear (**Figure 6**), but the bilinear extrapolation given by the standard leads to larger differences of around 5 %. Despite the irradiance of the affected points is lower than 100 W/m², a considerable amount of data points is affected, thus the difference in yield accumulates. It is also not recommended to set the efficiency to 0 at 0 W/m² irradiance when doing Energy Rating calculations, since this leads to a severe underestimation in the range of 0 – 100 W/m² irradiance, shown in **Figure 6**.

Figure 5: Difference of each Energy Rating power data point calculated with high resolution power matrix (blue squares) divided by power values of the low-resolution matrix (red dots).

Figure 6: Module efficiency at 25°C plotted over irradiance. The additional data point at 50 W/m² fits well to the slightly non-linear curve shape.

6 CONCLUSIONS

We measured the power matrix of a p-Si module with an LED-based solar simulator in a higher resolution

compared to the IEC 61853 standard recommendation. Differences at individual data points are apparent for certain G-T combinations and show plausible values. However, inter- and extrapolation issues are occurring in regions, where either few data points are apparent and / or the data points have a low irradiance, thus the differences are nearly not apparent in the yield. So at least for p-Si modules, we conclude that the current reduced amount of data points defined in the Energy Rating matrix are well defined. In fact, first parameter studies without the 75°C data point showed, that high-temperature power matrix values could be extrapolated sufficiently. In further studies, the high-resolution measurements will be repeated for different module technologies in order to provide a broader data basis for a possible simplification of the Energy Rating matrix.

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